

The Alan Turing Institute

Threat Taxonomy for Biometric Systems

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Threat Taxonomy for Biometric Systems

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Abstract

Biometric traits such as fingerprints, facial features, irises, and voices are unique and advantageous for identifying systems; yet, their permanent nature makes them susceptible to irreversible risks related to security, privacy, and fairness. As the dependence on biometric systems for authentication, surveillance, and identification increases, these challenges are also growing. Biometric systems have faced evolving threats over the past two decades, exposing vulnerabilities and motivating developments in security measures. Early incidents, such as spoofing with "gummy fingers" in 2002 and severe exploits like severed finger cases in 2005, exposed critical weaknesses. More recent threats include DeepFake attacks for biometric fabrication, large-scale breaches, and AI-driven spoofing, prompting innovations like multi-factor authentication and liveness detection. The increase in the access and availability of the AI-based tools caused significant changes in the threat landscape of biometric systems by raising further concerns about privacy, fairness, and ethics, especially with large-scale surveillance systems. Moreover, as quantum algorithms are developed, it becomes more feasible to break existing encryption mechanisms. Thus, there is an emerging requirement for the development of post-quantum cryptographic solutions. This study provides a taxonomy of threats to biometric data and systems, focusing on security breaches, privacy violations, and fairness concerns. It aims to provide a comprehensive list of threats for use in the development of more secure, privacy-preserving, and equitable biometric technologies.

1 Introduction

Biometric technologies are essential for modern security and surveillance frameworks for identity verification across a variety of domains, including border control, healthcare, banking, mobile devices, and public safety [1]. While these technologies offer significant advantages, they also present specific vulnerabilities. The evolution of biometric systems and the relevant technologies has shaped its threat landscape as well. While the early demonstration of spoofing used "gummy fingers", recent threats include large-scale data breaches exposing millions of biometric records and deepfake attacks for manipulating facial recognition systems [2, 3].

Threats to biometric systems may compromise security, privacy, and fairness, which may present an interrelationship between their objectives [4, 5]. Security threats, such as unauthorised access or breaches, can compromise the confidentiality, availability, or integrity of sensitive biometric data, exposing individuals to identity theft or system tampering. Privacy threats could compromise "personal information" collected and utilised in the system, which is the information that identifies, relates to, describes, is reasonably capable of being associated with, or could reason-

ably be linked, directly or indirectly, with a particular consumer or household. Similarly, threats may jeopardise the fairness of the system by embedding bias into the biometric algorithms or providing inequitable access to technology for the various groups or individuals among the society.

These threats are not isolated but interdependent and may contain synergies and tensions [6]. For example, security measures may conflict with privacy, as biometric authentication systems rely on the collection and processing of sensitive personal data. An honest-but-curious biometric system may use such data for over-surveillance of society or particular individuals. Similarly, inadequate use of privacy-preserving measures may limit the ability to detect and rectify biases, undermining fairness in the biometric algorithm or the data. Thus, addressing these threats requires a holistic approach that enables tailored integration of the security, privacy, and fairness measures to balance these properties.

This report aims to explore the evolving threat landscape of biometric systems and provide a taxonomy of the threats classified as security, privacy, and fairness. Deepfake biometric fabrication and malicious use of quantum algorithms have the potential to significantly change the threat landscape. Moreover, it

provides a timeline of the most significant security incidents that have occurred [7, 8, 9]. The scope of this report encompasses an in-depth analysis of biometric systems, their subsystems, and the processes involved in identity verification, based on academic literature, industry reports, and regulatory requirements. The key contributions of this report is as follows:

- A review of biometric systems for threat analysis, highlighting entry points and impacts on various processes and subsystems.
- An evaluation of emerging threats, including a timeline of major security incidents from the early 2000s to the day.
- A comprehensive list of threats to assist the researchers and engineers in developing secure, privacy-preserving, and fair biometric systems.

2 Preliminaries

This section provides an overview of biometric systems, including distinct physiological and behavioral traits [10], biometric subsystems as outlined in the ISO/IEC 24745 [11], key processes, and applications.

2.1 Biometric Traits

Biometric traits are broadly classified into two main categories as physiological and behavioral. Physiological features refer to bodily characteristics such as fingerprints, face patterns, and iris structure, while behavioral traits involve actions such as vocal patterns, typing rhythm, or stride [12]. These characteristics are employed since they are unique to each person and difficult to replicate. For a biometric trait to be useful, it must meet specific criteria [13]:

- **Universality:** All individuals should possess this trait to ensure widespread applicability.
- **Uniqueness:** The trait must vary considerably among individuals to minimise false matches.
- **Permanence:** The trait must be largely consistent throughout time to ensure long-term reliability.
- **Measurability:** The trait must be easily quantifiable and digitisable by sensors or devices.
- **Performance:** The system should achieve high accuracy with low False Acceptance Rate (FAR) and False Rejection Rate (FRR).
- **Acceptability:** Users must be willing to use the system and provide their biometric data.

- **Circumvention:** The system must resist spoofing or fraudulent manipulation.

2.1.1 Physiological Traits

Physiological traits involve the physical attributes of an individual. Typical instances include:

- **Fingerprint Recognition:** Captures the ridge and valley patterns on fingertips for identification.
- **Facial Recognition:** Analyses facial structures, such as the distance between eyes and nose shape, for recognition.
- **Iris and Retina Scanning:** Uses the unique patterns in the iris or blood vessels in the retina for secure identification.
- **Vascular Patterns:** Examines vein structures in hands or wrists for identification, particularly in systems requiring high security.

2.1.2 Behavioral Traits

Behavioral traits are based on the unique patterns of actions and interactions of individuals. These include:

- **Voice Recognition:** Analyses vocal patterns based on pitch, tone, and rhythm.
- **Gait Analysis:** Studies walking patterns to identify individuals, often captured via video or floor sensors.
- **Keystroke Dynamics:** Tracks typing speed and rhythm to differentiate users.
- **Signature Dynamics:** Captures the way an individual signs, including pen pressure and stroke order.

2.2 Biometric Systems

Biometric systems are vital for existing security frameworks since they provide reliable and robust authentication mechanisms based on individuals' unique physical and behavioural traits. Thus, they often provide enhanced security to mitigate the unauthorised access threats compared to the security frameworks depending on passwords or tokens. The ISO/IEC 24745 standard outlines a reference architecture for the design and implementation of biometric systems, comprising five interrelated subsystems: biometric data capture, signal processing, data storage, matching, and decision subsystems [11]. Each subsystem executes essential functions that collectively facilitate the biometric

system's precise and efficient implementation of authentication, identification, surveillance or deduplication. Figure 1 illustrates the reference architecture, highlighting integration and flow of information between subsystems.

2.2.1 Subsystems

Each subsystem is responsible for a particular step in the biometric data lifecycle, including the capture, processing, storage, comparison, and analysis of biometric data. The roles and interactions of subsystems are also needed for understanding the potential threat entry points and what possible paths could be followed by an adversary and what hazards could occur.

Biometric Data Capture Subsystem: This subsystem serves as the primary interface between the user and the biometric system. It employs specific sensors to capture biometric traits and transforms them into biometric samples. These sensors vary depending on the modality in use, such as optical and capacitive fingerprint scanners, cameras for facial recognition, and microphones for voice authentication [14].

The quality and accuracy of the captured data are critical, as they directly affect the system's performance in the following phases. Advanced sensors have been developed to address environmental challenges such as low-light conditions, motion artefacts, and noise [15]. For instance, multispectral fingerprint scanners enable capturing detailed representations of fingerprints for enhancing recognition accuracy for dirty or damaged fingerprint capturing [16]. Similarly, 3D facial recognition systems and depth cameras provide higher robustness against environmental variations in lighting and facial expressions compared to traditional 2D cameras [17]. Furthermore, noise cancellation and anti-spoofing mechanisms are often employed to enhance the reliability of the data capture process [18].

Signal Processing Subsystem: Once raw biometric data is captured, this subsystem extracts biometric features from the captured sample. It processes the raw biometric data into output numbers or labels that can be compared with those extracted from other biometric samples. This involves preprocessing steps including noise reduction, normalisation, and feature extraction [19]. These traits are then converted into a vectorial representation, which functions as the input for the matching process. The efficacy of the signal processing subsystem is critical to the system's resilience to fluctuations in lighting conditions, sensor quality, or minor alterations in the biometric trait. Recent studies

have demonstrated significant advancements in the processing of biometric templates by utilising deep neural networks (DNNs). For example, pre-trained convolutional neural network (CNN) models such as Inception, Xception and NasNetLarge could achieve recognition accuracy higher than 97% for a variety of fingerprint patterns, including whorls [20].

Data Storage Subsystem: The biometric references obtained in the enrollment process are stored in data storage subsystem. Biometric references are usually stored as biometric templates, which are mathematical representations of the collected features, instead of raw data to prevent reverse-engineering of the original biometric traits [21]. These templates are also often preserved in encrypted forms to prevent unauthorised access and ensure compliance with data protection regulations, such as GDPR. For example, template protection using cancelable biometrics is an effective method for securing stored templates. Techniques such as hashing and salting are employed to build resilient systems. Biohashing methods combine a pseudo-random number generator key with fingerprint minutiae features (e.g., ridge endings and bifurcations) to produce a unique and secure binary code called a Fingerhash [22].

Matching Subsystem: This subsystem compares features extracted from a new biometric sample against the stored references. There are two main types of comparison: verification (1:1 matching), in which the system checks to see if the person providing the biometric sample matches the claimed identity, and identification (1:N matching), in which the system uses a database of references to find out who the person is [23]. This subsystem employs techniques such as pattern recognition, machine learning, and deep learning to achieve high accuracy and minimise false positives or negatives. It is particularly important for biometric deduplication which is gaining further significance for maintaining data integrity in applications such as access control, financial transactions, or humanitarian aid distribution, where duplicate entries can lead to a security, operational, or resource allocation issues [24]. It employs methods for accurately identifying duplicates and maintaining privacy through techniques such as secure multiparty computation.

Decision Subsystem: The final determination based on the output of the matching process includes evaluating the similarity scores produced during matching against predefined thresholds [25]. The decision subsystem may also integrate additional contex-

Fig. 1: Reference Architecture of a Biometric System, taken from [11] (BR (Biometric Reference): Stored data used for comparison; IR (Identity Reference): Non-biometric attributes linked to an individual's identity.)

tual factors, such as the location of the authentication attempt, time of access, or user-specific behavioural traits. This multi-model approach helps minimise errors, reduce false positives or negatives, and ensure a secure and context-aware decision-making process.

2.2.2 Processes

The above subsystems facilitate three main processes as follows:

Enrollment: It is the initial process of registering an individual's biometric data into the system. During this phase, the biometric data capture subsystem collects the raw data, which is subsequently processed to extract features and generate a mathematical representation. This template is securely stored in the data storage subsystem, forming the reference against which future samples will be compared. The quality of the enrollment process is critical, as any errors or inaccuracies can adversely impact the system's performance during verification or identification processes.

It serves as the foundational process in biometric reduplication, as unique biometric data is captured, processed, and securely stored in the database for future comparisons. Thus, the accuracy of the reduplication process relies on the accuracy of the enrollment

data.

Verification: In this process, a one-to-one (i.e., 1:1) comparison is executed for matching newly captured biometric data against the user's previously stored template to confirm their claimed identity. This is typically used for authentication purposes.

The verification process is widely employed in applications such as unlocking personal devices, authorising financial transactions, and securing physical access. Biometric authentication improves simplicity and security by replacing conventional techniques such as passwords and PINs. However, it requires additional measures to protect biometric templates from data breaches, as compromised biometric data cannot be readily changed or reissued like passwords.

Identification: This involves a one-to-many (i.e., 1:n) comparison, where the captured biometric data is compared against all stored templates in the database to determine the individual's identity. While the term "identification" is sometimes used interchangeably with "verification," these are distinct processes. Verification involves a one-to-one (1:1) comparison to confirm that an individual matches the credentials they claim (e.g., a national ID card or passport). In contrast, identification determines who someone is

without their prior declaration. Identification could be employed in applications like law enforcement or targeted surveillance, where individuals are matched to known profiles. For instance, casinos may use biometric identification to match clients against a database of blacklisted gamblers [26]. However, national ID programs, electoral registration, or border management are primarily rely on verification to authenticate individuals, ensuring that their identity corresponds to previously established records.

Advanced surveillance employs technologies such as facial recognition, gait analysis, and behavioural detection to enhance the large-scale identification of individuals in real time. These systems are implemented in public areas to improve security by detecting possible threats, managing crowds, and monitoring individuals of interest. However, its deployment may raise concerns about data security, potential misuse, and ensuring fairness.

3 Timeline of the Major Incidents

The biometric systems evolved over the past two decades - were influenced by many notable incidents. Figure 2 presents a timeline highlighting major security-related incidents in biometric systems, with references provided as footnotes.

In 2002, researchers demonstrated the vulnerability of fingerprint systems using artificial “gummy fingers”, as an early spoofing technique which highlighted the need for improved biometric security mechanisms. In 2005, car thieves severed a man’s finger to bypass a vehicle’s biometric security system, highlighting the extreme lengths criminals could go to exploit biometric systems. While mitigation techniques have been introduced, over time more sophisticated methods are adopted by the threat actors.

In 2013, the Chaos Computer Club successfully demonstrated that Apple’s TouchID could be bypassed by using a fake fingerprint. By 2015, the threat landscape had expanded to include large-scale data breaches, such as the leak of 5.6 million fingerprint records belonging to U.S. government employees. Such incidents have provided lessons and motivation for enhancing the security of biometric systems and the reduction of systems reliance on single points of failure. Techniques include adoption of multi-factor authentication and randomised biometric processes. Additionally, liveness detection algorithms have been adopted to counter evolving spoofing techniques that are becoming more advanced and widespread.

The emergence of DeepFake technologies provided a novel and advanced tool to conduct spoofing attacks against biometric systems. DeepFakes are able to gen-

erate highly realistic synthetic biometric data that can bypass fingerprint, facial recognition, and voice authentication systems. These capabilities significantly increase risks to authentication processes and potentially enable identity theft to a larger scale. Hence, there is an ongoing need for the development of AI-based detection systems in order to preserve the integrity of biometric security.

The integration of AI-driven technologies into biometric surveillance systems has raised new concerns about privacy and fairness. For example, China’s deployment of large-scale AI-enhanced surveillance infrastructure demonstrates the growing role of biometrics in large-scale monitoring systems. While these systems can enhance public safety, they can be potentially used for tracking and controlling populations, requiring transparent legal and ethical measures. Furthermore, a biased algorithmic decision-making may have negative impacts, particularly for marginalised groups and minorities. For example, some facial recognition algorithms have higher error rates when identifying women and individuals with darker skin tones. This bias has led to cases of wrongful arrests, such as the incident of an African American man who was misidentified by the facial recognition system as a suspect and wrongfully arrested by the Detroit Police Department in the United States [27].

Future biometric threats could further use the convergence of advanced technologies. AI-generated disinformation campaigns, like those influencing elections, may be on the increase. Similarly, deepfake attacks targeting sectors, such as finance suggest that threat actors will continue the use of AI-driven tools to exploit vulnerabilities. Additionally, the increasing use of facial recognition in public spaces, such as stadiums, presents new challenges in balancing security with privacy in terms of linkability threats.

Another significant threat is the emergence of quantum computing, which may make it easier to break the current encryption techniques. For example, Shor’s algorithm has the potential for deciphering sensitive biometric information. Hence, there is an increasing need for the adoption of post-quantum cryptographic solutions in biometric systems.

AI-driven countermeasures can also enhance the protection against adversarial machine learning attacks. However, the deployment of such technologies must address key ethical concerns, including privacy protection, data security, and algorithmic bias. Clearview AI received a \$33 million fine for its unauthorised facial recognition database due to recent regulatory actions. Transparency, fairness, and accountability are vital to establishing public trust and realising the potential benefits of these systems.

Fig. 2: Timeline of the Major Incidents to Biometric System

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Fig. 3: Taxonomy of Threats to Biometric Systems

4 Threat Taxonomy

This section presents a taxonomy of threats to biometric systems. Biometric systems, while providing robust security measures, are vulnerable to a diverse set of threat vectors. It is because they rely on physical and digital systems, highly sensitive data processing, and integration with sensitive functions such as identification, authentication, and surveillance. Such features produce multiple exposure points, requiring a detailed understanding of the threats that may jeopardise the system's confidentiality, integrity, availability, privacy, or fairness. Thus, the taxonomy categorises these threats into: security, privacy and fairness. Figure 3 provides a visual representation of the threat taxonomy for biometric systems.

4.1 Security Threats

The security threats could either directly target the physical components, such as the hardware, sensors, and environment in which they operate, or the system's architecture, operations, and operational procedures. If an adversary interacts directly with the biometric system, the main goal could be to compromise the subsystems that capture data and process signals. However, the vulnerabilities within the digital infrastructure, algorithms, or operational workflows could be exploited as well.

4.1.1 Sensor-Level Threats

Various entry points could be exploited for sensor-level threats. This includes physical access to sensors such as fingerprint scanners, cameras, or microphones, which can be tampered with or manipulated directly. Another entry point is the external presentation of spoofing materials, such as fake fingerprints or facial images, to deceive the system [28]. Environmental conditions like poor lighting or loud noise are also among the threats, as they can interfere with the accurate capture of biometric data. The above threats can significantly impact all of the processes in biometric systems. During enrollment, poor-quality or manipulated data captured due to these vulnerabilities can lead to the creation of inaccurate templates. This compromises the integrity of the system from the outset. In the verification and identification processes, spoofing attacks or degraded sensor performance resulting from these threats can cause either the false acceptance of unauthorised individuals or the false rejection of legitimate users. The key sensor-level threats are as follows:

- Presentation Attacks (i.e., Spoofing): These at-

tacks involve the use of artificial inputs such as face masks, photographs, synthetic voices, AI-generated faces, or deepfake videos to mislead biometric sensors.

- Sensor Tampering: This includes manipulations, such as lens scratches or the application of oil or dirt to degrade the functionality of biometric sensors.
- Sensor Skimming: This includes attaching external devices, such as fake fingerprint scanners, to intercept biometric inputs.
- Physical Damage: This includes deliberate actions to destroy sensors and system operations.

4.1.2 Raw Biometric Data-Level Threats

These threats pose significant risks to the integrity of biometric systems, jeopardising them through two main entry points. Attackers may intercept raw biometric data at the point of capture, gaining access to highly sensitive information before it is being transformed or encrypted and stored on the systems database [9]. Second, through signal jamming or deliberate noise injection, the quality and accuracy of the captured data could be compromised. The following threats are the main raw-biometric data-level threats:

- Physical Theft of Biometric Features: This includes the theft of physical biometric traits, such as severed fingers or stolen masks, to bypass systems.
- Forced Biometric Submission: This occurs when individuals are forced to provide their biometric data, such as fingerprints or facial scans.
- Long-Range Biometric Capturing: This refers to the use of long-distance cameras, microphones, or thermal sensors to collect biometric data without the individual's consent.
- Contactless Cloning: This involves cloning publicly accessible biometric traits, such as faces or voices, for fraudulent purposes.
- Morphing Attacks: This refers to combining biometric traits from two individuals to create a shared or fake identity.

4.1.3 Supply Chain Threats

Supply chain threats could pose significant security challenges to biometric systems, including hardware

and software manufacturing, transportation, and installation phases. During manufacturing, adversaries may integrate hardware or software components with malicious functionalities, undermining system integrity. Furthermore, the transportation and installation phases present opportunities for unauthorised modifications to hardware or software components, increasing the system's vulnerability[29]. The following list contains the major supply chain threats:

- **Malicious Hardware Integration:** This involves embedding vulnerabilities or malicious components during the manufacturing of biometric devices.
- **Compromised Logistics:** This refers to intercepting biometric devices during transit and tampering with or replacing their components.
- **Firmware Exploits:** This involves exploiting vulnerabilities or backdoors in embedded systems during the manufacturing of or assembly of devices to gain unauthorised access to biometric systems.

4.1.4 Environmental Disruption

This category of threat includes a range of factors that can disrupt the regular operation of devices and processes. The environment, whether naturally occurring or through manipulation can significantly degrade the quality of the biometric samples collected during enrollment. Poor sample quality invariably leads to increased error rates, manifesting as either false rejections or false acceptances.

- **Power and Signal Interference:** This includes the use of electromagnetic or radio frequency interference to disrupt biometric sensors or communication channels.
- **Thermal Attacks:** These attacks use extreme heat or cold to disable thermal-based sensors, such as those used for iris or vein detection.
- **Acoustic Disruption:** It involves the use of high-decibel or ultrasonic noises to impair the functioning of voice recognition systems.
- **Ambient Condition Manipulation:** This refers to altering environmental factors, such as lighting or noise, to degrade the performance of biometric systems.
- **Environmental Contamination:** It includes accidental introduction of substances, such as dust, oils, or chemicals, to obscure sensors and reduce their functionality.

4.1.5 Biometric Template-Level Threats

The primary entry point for these threats is unauthorised access to databases storing biometric templates to reconstruct original biometric traits. The impact of such threats on biometric processes is profound and far-reaching. In the context of verification and identification, compromised templates—whether stolen or modified—can facilitate unauthorised access to secure systems or enable sophisticated identity spoofing attacks.

- **Template Inversion:** This refers to the reverse-engineering of stored biometric templates to reconstruct original biometric traits.
- **Template Theft:** This involves the unauthorised access and theft of biometric templates during database breaches.
- **Template Modification:** This refers to tampering with stored templates to introduce errors or to cause denial of access.
- **Template Deletion:** This involves the removal of stored templates to deny legitimate users access to the biometric system.

4.1.6 Communication and Transmission Threats

These threats primarily exploit vulnerabilities in the data transmission process between the subsystems. These vulnerabilities can have severe impacts on critical processes within the biometric system. During the verification process, intercepted data can be reused for replay attacks, jeopardising the integrity of the system. Similarly, during the matching process, data that has been altered in transit can lead to false matches, compromising the accuracy and trustworthiness of the biometric authentication.

- **Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) Attacks:** These attacks involve intercepting biometric data during transmission between sensors and systems.
- **Replay Attacks:** This occurs when captured biometric data is reused to gain unauthorised access.
- **Eavesdropping:** It refers to the unauthorised interception of biometric data communication.

4.1.7 Algorithmic Threats

The primary entry points of these threats are the manipulation of training data or injection of adversarial examples or the exploitation of vulnerabilities in matching algorithms. In the signal processing and matching subsystems, these threats can sub-

stantially reduce recognition accuracy, leading to increased rates of both false acceptances and false rejections. Moreover, in the decision-making, algorithmic biases—whether inherent or introduced—can result in unfair outcomes during identification, potentially discriminating against certain demographic groups.

- **Adversarial Inputs:** These are manipulated inputs designed to exploit weaknesses in AI algorithms, causing false positives or false negatives.
- **Identity Impersonation:** This involves the use of synthetic biometric data to mimic the identity of another individual.
- **Bias and Discrimination:** This occurs when algorithms demonstrate deliberate disparate accuracy or utility among various demographic groups.
- **Model Poisoning:** It refers to the corruption of training datasets, leading to degraded performance of biometric models.
- **Data Poisoning:** This involves inserting manipulated or corrupt biometric samples into training datasets, introducing errors or biases.
- **Software Exploits:** These target unpatched vulnerabilities in biometric software to compromise the system.
- **Matching Threshold Manipulation:** It refers to altering the matching threshold to increase false acceptances or rejections.

4.1.8 Operational Threats

These threats can be categorised into two main entry points: misconfigurations during system setup, which involve errors or oversights in the initial configuration of biometric systems, and overloading the system with requests, such as Denial of Service (DoS), by flooding it with a high volume of requests, potentially rendering it unresponsive. Operational threats can prevent enrollment, verification, and identification.

- **Availability Threats:** This includes denial-of-service (DoS) assaults or power outages that aim to disable biometric systems.
- **Integrity Threats:** This involves exploiting intentional or unintentional vulnerabilities in a biometric system's software, hardware, or operational processes to allow unauthorised access or manipulation. The system's integrity could be undermined through such vulnerabilities, and an attacker could bypass standard authentication mechanisms or alter critical functions without detection.

4.1.9 Insider Threats

These threats originate from individuals who have authorised access to the system, which makes them particularly challenging to detect and mitigate. The entry points include misuse of access privileges for altering system configurations, accessing sensitive data, modifying system parameters, or creating vulnerabilities.

- **Malicious Insider:** This occurs when individuals with privileged access intentionally leak or compromise biometric data.
- **Accidental Data Leakage:** This refers to the unintended leak of biometric data due to unsecured data handling and storage processes.

4.2 Privacy Threats

Privacy threats arise from the misuse, leakage, or unauthorised sharing of biometric data, leading to a range of risks, including identity theft, unauthorised surveillance, and discrimination. These threats primarily concern the data storage subsystem, but affecting all processes by compromising user privacy and trust. LINDDUN framework, a privacy threat analysis methodology, is considered for this category and applied to biometric systems. Under LINDDUN, privacy threats are categorised into distinct groups, such as linking, identification, non-repudiation, detecting, disclosure, unawareness, and non-compliance and biometric-specific threats have been mapped to these categories [30, 31].

4.2.1 Linking Threats

It includes associating multiple pieces of data or user actions to infer new information about individuals or groups, even without directly identifying them.

- **Inferring Profiles:** This occurs when biometric data is combined with external data (e.g., location, behaviour) to generate detailed user profiles without consent. For example, a workplace biometric attendance system linked with individuals' productivity stats can infer performance profiles.
- **Group Profiling:** This refers to the aggregation of data to make assumptions or stereotypes about demographic groups. For example, health insurance companies may use facial recognition to classify individuals based on "predicted" health risks.
- **Data Correlation:** This involves combining biometric data with external records to infer sensitive contexts or information. For example, biometric attendance monitoring at medical clinics

could reveal sensitive information about an individual's history, such as addiction treatments or mental health counselling.

- **Unintended Surveillance:** This refers to the use of biometric systems for purposes beyond their intended applications without their consent. For example, by monitoring the use of biometric data, system administrators could track individuals' activities or locations, enabling unauthorised or unethical surveillance. Such misuse raises significant privacy concerns and highlights the importance of implementing strict usage policies and oversight mechanisms to prevent abuse.

4.2.2 Identification Threats

Identifying threats may occur when biometric traits, such as voice, gait, or iris patterns, are used to determine an individual's identity. These threats exploit the uniqueness of biometric data to link individuals to specific activities, locations, or contexts, potentially compromising their privacy.

For example, gait recognition patterns captured from public surveillance footage could be analysed and cross-referenced with other data sources to reveal an individual's identity, even if there were no prior interactions with the system. Identifying threats highlights the broader privacy implications of biometric systems and emphasises the need for strict regulatory controls, transparency, and consent-based usage to ensure that biometric data is not exploited beyond its legitimate purposes, such as identifying the individuals.

Unlike identifying individuals through security breaches often initiated by attackers, identifying threats in the context of privacy can occur in non-malicious settings. For example, a system administrator with honest-but-curious intentions may use their access to link biometric data with unrelated activities or contexts, which can compromise user privacy.

4.2.3 Non-Repudiation Threats

Non-repudiation as a privacy threat arises when an individual's actions or biometric data usage logs are permanently linked to their identity, eliminating the possibility of plausible deniability. This occurs due to the system's ability to retain detailed records of activities, such as log files, digital signatures, metadata, or watermarked data. While these records are essential for ensuring security and accountability, they also pose significant privacy risks if misused or disclosed.

Such threats can be exploited by an honest-but-curious threat actor — without malicious intent, examining these records beyond their intended purpose.

Additionally, unauthorised disclosure of these records could reveal sensitive personal information, potentially compromising individuals' privacy and security. Thus, the balance between the requirements for security and privacy could be needed.

4.2.4 Detection Threats

Detection as a privacy threat may occur if an adversary monitors the communication signals of biometric systems to infer user interactions or device activities. Even without accessing the actual biometric data, adversaries can exploit system usage patterns to deduce sensitive information. For instance, simply detecting that a biometric authentication system is in use at a specific location could reveal a user's presence there, potentially compromising their privacy. This type of threat does not involve detecting vulnerabilities or threats but rather focuses on the privacy risks associated with monitoring and inferring data from system activities.

4.2.5 Data Disclosure Threats

Data disclosure threats may emerge due to the excessive or unnecessary collection, processing, or sharing of biometric data, which can compromise user privacy and increase the risk of misuse. The main examples of data disclosure threats include:

- **Inadequate Data Minimisation:** Biometric systems may collect and store more data than necessary or retain it beyond its useful period. For example, a gym may require facial scans for access instead of relying on simple methods like membership cards, which unnecessarily increase the risk of privacy breaches.
- **Third-Party Data Sharing:** This refers to sharing biometric data with external entities for purposes such as analytics or marketing without user consent. For instance, a smart home system could share voice recordings with advertisers to tailor product recommendations.

4.2.6 Unawareness Threats

Individuals may be unaware or lack control over how their biometric data is collected, processed, or stored. For example, a retail store may use facial recognition cameras to analyse visitor demographics without notifying customers without any consent. Similarly, users may lack the ability to delete their biometric templates or revoke access for a system. An example of this is a biometric access system could introduce cloud storage

for templates without informing users of such change. Such threats could be mitigated by integrating transparency, user consent, and robust data governance in biometric systems.

4.2.7 Non-Compliance Threats

These threats include deviations from best practices, regulations, or legal standards.

- **Regulatory Misalignment:** Biometric systems may fail to comply with regulations, such as the GDPR or national privacy laws.
- **Lack of Risk Assessments:** This refers to the deployment of biometric systems without properly assessing their potential privacy impacts. For instance, a school implementing facial recognition for attendance might fail to evaluate the risks associated with storing and processing student data.
- **Cross-Jurisdictional Issues:** Biometric systems could be globally interconnected, and privacy regulations could vary across different regions. Thus, there could be privacy compliance issues.

4.3 Fairness Threats

Fairness in biometric systems pose a significant concern, primarily affecting the signal processing and decision subsystems. These threats could potentially impact the enrollment and identification processes, jeopardising the equity and reliability of biometric systems, particularly across diverse user populations [32]. Fairness issues in biometric systems can emerge due to security breaches caused by malicious actors; however, the threats categorised under fairness are distinct since they are not caused by an attacker but by biases or inequities inherent within the system itself, such as flawed algorithms, unrepresentative training data, or design limitations, which result in unequal or discriminatory outcomes for users.

A key aspect of fairness threats is bias in recognition, this issue arises from security issues during system design or training. The first entry point that may contribute to this issue is the bias that can exist in training datasets, where the quality and diversity of data used to train recognition algorithms fail to adequately represent various demographics, such as ethnicities, age groups, or genders. This lack of representation can result in algorithms that perform disproportionately well for certain groups while under-performing for others. The other entry point is improper tuning of recognition algorithms, which may introduce or exacerbate bias, even when diverse

training data is available. Inadequate consideration of demographic variations during algorithm optimisation—such as in feature extraction, matching thresholds, or decision boundaries—can lead to disparate performance outcomes.

During the enrollment process, biased recognition may lead to inadequate or inaccurate template generation for under-represented groups, resulting in lower-quality templates that predispose these users to errors during subsequent identification attempts.

In the identification process, bias may cause unequal error rates across demographic groups, including higher false rejection rates for certain populations, potentially leading to denied access or services, and higher false acceptance rates for others, which could compromise security.

4.3.1 Bias in Recognition

This threat includes disparities in performance for certain demographic groups, often due to biased training data [33]. For instance, if training datasets are not representative of diverse populations, the system may exhibit higher error rates for under-represented groups. This can lead to unintended consequences, including restricting access to services and misidentification for these groups. Such biases often arise from historical inequities in data collection processes, where majority groups are over-represented while minority groups are under-represented. For example, early image datasets used for facial recognition disproportionately featured individuals with light skin tones, leading to significant accuracy gaps when applied to darker-skinned individuals [34]. This issue is compounded by the reliance on pre-existing datasets that often embed societal biases into the training process.

4.3.2 Unequal Error Rates

This involves higher false positive or negative rates for specific groups of people. For instance, a system might more often restrict valid access attempts from older adults or people with special biometric features, such as fingerprints that are damaged, or it could give higher rates of false acceptance to those groups. It can arise due to variations in biometric patterns that are not well-represented during system training. For instance, older adults may encounter challenges with fingerprint recognition systems due to their clarity in capturing ridges, resulting in increased false rejection rates. Similarly, the error rate may vary significantly across demographic lines, with factors such as age, gender, and physical conditions playing a role. Furthermore, in facial recognition, differences in the way facial features are captured and processed for individ-

uals of varying skin tones have led to substantial discrepancies in error rates, often disadvantaging minority groups [35, 36].

4.3.3 Accessibility Exclusion

This refers to the exclusion of individuals with physical impairments or non-standard biometric traits. For example, individuals with missing fingers, facial disfigurements, or unique physical conditions may find themselves excluded from systems that rely on standard biometric features, raising concerns about their fairness. Biometric systems often depend on templates derived from usual traits, and they may neglect outliers with non-standard traits. For instance, people with disfigurements on their faces might be misclassified or even rejected outright. People with unique physical traits, such as genetic conditions that change biometric patterns, may also have more problems [37, 38].

5 Discussion and Summary

The significance of biometric systems for security and surveillance frameworks is growing, as they are increasingly utilised for identity verification in various sectors, such as healthcare, banking, border control, and public safety. This report presents a comprehensive taxonomy of threats to biometric systems, emphasising the interconnected challenges of security, privacy, and fairness. For instance, security threats could be used to conduct algorithmic manipulation or template theft, which are fairness and privacy issues, respectively. Thus, it is required to address these threats in a comprehensive way rather than focusing on one of them. Furthermore, the report reviews the evolution of these threats through a timeline of incidents, from early spoofing demonstrations to sophisticated deepfake biometric generation attacks. The threat categories are as follows:

- Security Threats: These include physical and digital threats, such as spoofing, sensor tampering, and algorithmic manipulations, as well as emerging threats such as deepfake biometric fabrication and malicious use of quantum algorithms.
- Privacy threats: These include concerns about the misuse and unauthorised access of biometric data, leading to issues including linking, identification, non-repudiation, detection, data disclosure, unawareness, and non-compliance.
- Fairness Threats: These include threats causing bias in recognition algorithms, unequal error rates, and accessibility exclusions that disproportionately affect certain demographics.

In addition to the identified threats, there are emerging tools and techniques that pose novel ways to attack biometric systems. Deepfake technologies are threatening the security of biometric systems by creating real-like synthetic biometric traits [3]. An adversary may use AI-generated synthetic biometric traits during data capture, creating fake biometric data, such as realistic faces, voices, or fingerprints. Additionally, deepfake technology can facilitate generating manipulated video or audio content [39, 40].

However, a wide range of countermeasures are also integrated into biometric systems to enhance the system's resistance to spoofing, data breaches, and privacy violations. Liveness detection mechanisms verify that the biometric sample originates from a living individual rather than a spoofed artefact, such as masks, fake fingerprints, or deepfake videos [41].

Another critical challenge is the emergence of the quantum algorithms which can undermine existing cryptographic foundations used in protection of biometric data [42]. Quantum algorithms, such as Shor's algorithm [43], will be able to break the majority of existing encryption methods once sufficiently advanced quantum computers become available. This capability would enable attackers to decrypt stored biometric templates and compromise data confidentiality, highlighting the urgent need for the development and adoption of quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions for maintaining the confidentiality.

These algorithms could decrypt previously secure biometric templates, exposing sensitive personal information, as encrypted data could be collected today and decrypted in the future as the technology advances. In the biometric matching process, compromised templates may result in unauthorised access, identity theft, and a loss of trust in biometric authentication systems. However, there are ongoing efforts to standardise post-quantum cryptography (PQC) methods to accelerate the adoption of quantum-resistant algorithms [44]. Government agencies, including the U.S. Customs and Border Protection, are already integrating PQC to safeguard sensitive data, including biometrics [45]. Additionally, innovative quantum-resistant biometric solutions, such as the Irreversibly Transformed Identity Token are being developed [46].

Ensuring secure, private, and fair biometric systems remains a significant challenge, given the multifaceted vulnerabilities in data protection, the potential for misuse or unauthorised access, and the persistent biases that disproportionately impact under-represented demographic groups. The implementation of robust privacy-preserving techniques and assured fairness are a must to maintain system performance and trustworthiness.

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